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Research Article

**THE STUDY OF ANEMIA PREVALENCE IN PREGNANT
WOMEN OF MULTAN**¹Sher Muhammad Khan, ²Muhammad Ahmed Khan, ³Muhammad Waqas¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan.²The University Of Lahore, Lahore.³King Edward Medical University, Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine anaemia prevalence in pregnant women of the Multan**Design & duration:** It is a descriptive type of cross-sectional study completed in 6 months.**Setting:** This study is held in the obstetrics and gynaecology department of Nishtar Hospital Multan and it is a type of multicentric study.**Patients & methods:** Women with pregnancy lived in the city of Pakistan, Multan, reporting to Nishtar Hospital Multan in an outpatient door. After the complete examination and complete history USG (ultrasonography) for fetus health done. Haemoglobin level of pregnant women in the study group was tested. The consecutive sampling of Non-probability technique was used. All the data was calculated on a proforma which was pre-designed proforma. SPSS software was used to analyze the data. standard deviation, means, frequency, and Percentage were calculated. The test of Chi-square was applied. Pregnant Women admitted in ICU or having comorbidities were not included in this study.**Results:** Total 850 pregnant women cases were studied, from which 300 pregnant women (35.3%) were anaemic. 25% pregnant women were primigravida, 36.7% gravida-2 pregnant women, and 38.3% gravida \geq 3 pregnant women. 3. The women having Hb level below 7g/dl were 7%, between 7 to 8g/dl were 42%, 8.1 to 9g/dl were 34.7% pregnant women, and Hb level 9.1 to 10g/dl were 19.7% pregnant women.**Conclusion:** Anemia is more common condition in pregnant women of Multan, especially in multigravida women. Moderate types of anaemia are much more common than milder and severe forms.**Keywords:** Anemia, Pregnant women, Primigravida, Multigravida**Corresponding author:****Sher Muhammad Khan.,**

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INTRODUCTION:

During pregnancy, many physiological changes occur in women body. 1-3 Blood plasma volume is increased due to hormonal changes; hence the Hb level is decreased. Serum level of hematocrit, RBCs count, ferritin and iron concentration is decreased. In pregnancy, the iron requirement is increased up to 2.5-6.6 mg/day. 4-6 If the demand for iron is not compensated, then anaemia is developed. About 30-50% of pregnant women face iron deficiency anaemia. It is a medical condition in which haemoglobin concentration in blood is lower than the average level according to age gender and the environment resulting in decreased oxygen-carrying capacity in the blood. 7,8 According to WHO anaemia is defined as Hb concentration less than 11 g/dl and in severe anaemia it is <7g/dl. A most common type is iron-deficiency anaemia in 90% patients and folic acid anaemia in 5% cases. 9-11 Prevalence of pregnancy-induced anaemia is higher in developing and underdeveloped countries. According to K. Kalaiyani *et al.*, the prevalence of anaemia in South Asian countries is the highest globally. Its high prevalence in these countries is low socioeconomic status, low literacy rate, poor hygiene, eating habits and other cultural factors.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This is a cross-sectional study held in the obstetrics and gynaecology department of tertiary care hospitals, Nishtar Hospital Multan. The study was started in

January and completed in June 2020 after six months duration. Pregnant women live in the Multan reporting to Nishtar Hospital Multan in and outpatient doors. After the complete examination and complete history USG (ultrasonography) for fetus health done. Haemoglobin level of all the pregnant women in this study group was tested. The consecutive sampling of Non-probability technique was used. All the data was calculated on a proforma which was pre-designed proforma. SPSS software was used to analyze the data. standard deviation, means, frequency, and Percentage were calculated. The test of Chi-square was applied. Pregnant Women admitted in ICU or having comorbidities were not included in this study. Pregnant women of all trimesters were included in the study. Other women receiving therapy for anaemia, history of massive bleeding, history of recent blood transfusion or chronic medical illness such as thalassemia, chronic renal failure, chronic liver disease and rheumatoid arthritis were excluded from the study.

RESULTS:

Total 850 pregnant women cases were studied, from which 300 pregnant women (35.3%) were anaemic. 25% pregnant women were primigravida, 36.7% gravida-2 pregnant women, and 38.3% gravida \geq 3 pregnant women. 3. The women having Hb level below 7g/dl were 7%, between 7 to 8g/dl were 42%, 8.1 to 9g/dl were 34.7% pregnant women, and Hb level 9.1 to 10g/dl were 19.7% pregnant women.

(Table-1) Hb level among study group cases

Hemoglobin level (g/dl)	N	%
<7	11	3.7
7-8	126	42
8.1-9	104	34.7
9-10	59	19.7

(Figure-1) Hb level among primigravida (n=75)

(Figure-2) Hb level among gravida ≥ 2 (n=225)

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted to determine the frequency of anaemic pregnant women in the multan city. In this study prevalence was 35.3%. Prevalence rate ranges from 35-75% in different countries.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ In south Asian countries, maternal morbidity and mortality are higher than in other countries. According to previous studies conducted in India, the prevalence of pregnancy-induced anaemia was 33-100%.¹⁹ In India, anaemia is the second most common cause of maternal death, contributing 20% of total maternal deaths.²⁰ During pregnancy, many physiological changes occur in women's bodies. Blood plasma volume is increased due to hormonal changes; hence the Hb level is decreased. Serum level of hematocrit, RBCs count, ferritin and iron concentration is decreased. In pregnancy, the iron requirement is increased up to 2.5-

6.6 mg/day.^{21,22} If the demand for iron is not compensated, then anaemia is developed.

About 30-50% of pregnant women face iron deficiency anaemia. It is a medical condition in which haemoglobin concentration in blood is lower than average level according to age, gender and environment, resulting in decreased oxygen-carrying capacity in the blood. This is a cross-sectional study conducted in the gynaecology and obstetrics department of tertiary care hospitals, Nishtar Hospital multan. The study was started in January and completed in June 2020 after six months duration. Pregnant women live in multan city reporting to Nishtar Hospital Multan in and outpatient doors. After the history and complete examination ultrasonography for fetal well being done. Haemoglobin level of all cases in the study group was tested.

Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used. Total 850 cases were studied out of which 300(35.3%) pregnant women were anaemic. There were 75(25%) women primigravida, 110(36.7%) women were gravida-2, and 115(38.3%) women were gravida ≥ 3 . According to K. Kalaivani *et al.*, the prevalence of anaemia in South Asian countries is highest globally. Its high prevalence in these countries is low socioeconomic status, low literacy rate, poor hygiene, eating habits and other cultural factors.²³ When a lady has already depleted iron stores and enters into pregnancy, anaemia worsens leading to many complications. As a result, the maternal and fetal mortality rate is increased.

CONCLUSION:

Due to low diet and hygiene, anaemia is a common problem among pregnant women in our population, especially in multigravida women. Moderate types of anaemia are much more common than mild and severe forms. Adequate maternal screening for anaemia is necessary. Women should be educated about diet and hygiene. Antenatal care plays an essential role in this aspect.

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